

Private Lives: The Work of Mathematics Leaders in Irish Primary Schools

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Little is known of the enactment of subject-specific leadership across our education system. This national deficiency is aptly exemplified by our collective ignorance of mathematics leadership in the primary school sector. This research sought to address this gap by focusing upon ten individuals who self-identified as local mathematics leaders. Specific strands of inquiry included the nature of their duties, their generalised working habits, the supports they accessed and the skillset that they called upon in their work. Three research instruments were utilised to gather data: an initial participant questionnaire/profiler, a twenty-day participant activity log and a semi-structured interview format at the conclusion of the logging period. Following the merger of qualitative and quantitative data bases, a set of five cross-participant themes were identified for elucidation. Primarily, the themes addressed key findings encapsulating the critical influence of context upon the working emphases of the mathematics leader, the ever-growing complexity of the role, seeming contradictions within such leadership work, the universal absence of adequate time for mathematics leaders to lead, and, the apparent dearth of bespoke professional development and networking opportunities available to such personnel. This paper summarises the findings of an EdD. dissertation.

The Context

The critical influence of school leadership upon teacher efficacy and subsequent pupil outcomes is now an uncontested truth of modern education (Heck and Hallinger, 2014; Vale et al., 2010, and, Leithwood et al., 2008). Indeed, the latter authors emphatically note that “leadership acts as a catalyst without which other good things are quite unlikely to happen” (2008, p.28). This correlation between leadership efficacy and broader educational effectiveness has led to an understandable explosion in the literature dedicated to school leadership, particularly over the last two decades, both nationally and internationally. However, despite this enhanced examination of school leadership in Ireland particularly, little is known of the enactment of subject-specific leadership in the Irish context. Nowhere is this malaise more evident than in our unawareness of mathematics leadership in the primary sector. As Mathematics remains a core curricular area in our primary education syllabus, this lacunae is particularly unsettling. Coincidentally, this recognition also comes at a time of growing expectation being placed upon the mathematics teaching and learning provision in all schools (Department of Education and Skills (DES), 2017). Mathematics is not unique in this regard – across Ireland’s primary and second-level sectors, middle and senior school leaders are being challenged to lead diverse curricular areas, each with their own intricacies and specialised demands. Policy makers are hungry for improvement in each discipline but are leaders adequately supported to realise these lofty ambitions? Are current leadership constructs enabling or undermining this drive? The practical leadership of mathematics as enacted in our primary schools, and as captured in this paper, provides an illustrative context to attempt to answer these questions. It is uncontested that school leaders cannot lead without assistance. Therefore, the research also strives to identify, and amplify the clamour for,

practical supports and structures that mathematics leaders distinguish as being crucial to sustain their important work.

Learnings from the Literature

The research illustrates that distributed leadership patterns retain a strong foothold in most international school systems (Liu, 2020). Ireland's recently rebooted middle-management structures, still cling to the coattails of this international movement (Lárusdóttir and O'Connor, 2017). However, even the distributed model comes with the caveat that an authentic form of shared leadership requires the ceding of real power and influence to other competent, supported co-leaders (Shava and Tlou, 2018). Whilst alternative leadership styles tend to prioritise the people within the school organisation (such as transformational or servant leadership approaches), it is perhaps the instructional approach that best responds to the demands and specialisation of curricular leadership. Its emphasis on enhancing classroom pedagogy is as alluring as it is simplistic. Katterfeld teases out the practical implication of this style – the elucidation of academic purpose and high expectations, coupled with the creation of a “schoolwide focus on instruction through monitoring the progress of teaching and learning” (2014, p.1127). The Department of Education and Skills updated *Looking at Our Schools* leadership framework (2016) does begin to address the practical steps towards such an instructionally-focused form of school leadership in an Irish context. However, it's generalised, non-subject specific context is a missed opportunity to prioritise effective curriculum leadership. Similarly, the most recent DES circular (2018) aimed at reforming school leadership structures makes a small number of vague references to responsibility for curriculum development and implementation, but without any explicit subject-specific application. Indeed, the initially promising *Numeracy Link Teacher* role, first mooted during the early implementation of school self-evaluation in Ireland a decade ago, appears to have disappeared without trace within the primary school system. In this troubling context, it is particularly crucial to keep sight of the extensive international literature which links hands-on mathematics leadership and an improved instructional environment for pupils (Heck and Hallinger, 2014).

In the absence of relevant Irish research, the international literature reinforces the real phenomenon of localised mathematics leadership. Such activity is spearheaded by an assortment of constructs drawing from principal teachers, formally appointed middle management staff, volunteers and collaborative multi-member pods. The unique credibility of teacher leaders leading curriculum innovation and improvement among colleagues is a standout feature of the research (Jorgensen, 2016). Supports for these assorted leadership constructs varies from territory to territory, but Irish equivalents must enviously regard the dedicated release time, ongoing state-funded professional development and networking opportunities that are the norm elsewhere. In reality, a vast miscellany of curricular, pedagogical and organisational duties form the bedrock of these leaders' work (See Grootenboer et al., 2015; Sexton and Downton, 2014; Firestone and Martinez, 2007; Millett et al., 2004). Indeed, this specific literature directly contributed to the authors' isolating twelve commonly-accepted key mathematics leadership duties (See Table 1). It should be noted that

this list is not exhaustive, but does convey the sheer breadth of the role. This survey formed an essential building block of this study. Furthermore, it should be acknowledged that with the guiding influence of subject-specific leadership charters, there currently exists a concerted effort in many North American school districts, as just one international example, to cover all the bases of mathematics leadership (See Balka et al., 2010; National Council of Supervisors of Mathematics, 2008 as exemplars of such guidance).

Table 1

Identified Duties of School Mathematics Leaders

1. Curating and/or (re)developing the school plan for Mathematics.
2. Articulating the school's agreed vision for the teaching and learning of Mathematics.
3. Coordinating ongoing school self-evaluation processes in Numeracy.
4. Procuring, organising or distributing resources to teach Mathematics.
5. Informing colleagues of CPD opportunities and other new developments in the area of Mathematics.
6. Promoting the status and importance of Mathematics in the broader school community.
7. Advising and mentoring new colleagues on mathematics-specific teaching, learning and planning issues.
8. Advising and mentoring existing colleagues on mathematics-specific teaching, learning and planning issues.
9. Engaging with external services/providers to enhance the provision of mathematics teaching within the school.
10. Preparing materials for, and/or involvement in the administration of, student mathematics testing/other assessment.
11. Monitoring the standards of mathematics teaching and learning within the school.
12. Seeking and/or utilising the support of parents to enhance the teaching and learning capacity of Mathematics in school and/or at home.

This Research Project

This research focused upon ten individuals who self-identified as mathematics leaders. The representative cohort were drawn from both the principal (administrative and teaching) and teacher-leader communities. Leaders from DEIS, non-DEIS, rural, urban, developing and Irish language medium schools were represented in the sample. Some of the teacher leaders were unpaid volunteers who held a particular affinity for the subject. Specific strands of inquiry included the nature of the duties these mathematics leaders undertook, their generalised working habits, the supports they accessed and the precise skillset they exploited in their work. Data was gathered through an initial participant questionnaire/profiler, a subsequent twenty-day participant activity log and finally, a semi-structured interview format which built upon the insights gleaned from the logging data. Of the three instruments, the questionnaire/profiler provided the majority of qualitative data for the study. Inspired by Spillane and Zuberi's (2009, p.375) *Leadership Daily Practice Log*, each mathematics-leader participant was asked to complete a log of their mathematics leadership-related activities for a staggered four-week period during the 2018/19 school year. Additional detail (whether spontaneous or pre-planned, its scheduling and duration, the expertise it required and its

overall effectiveness) was sought per logged action. For context, a screenshot of a completed page from one anonymised participant log is provided (See Figure 1).

Figure 1

Extract from Participant Activity Log

Day and Date: Tuesday 29th January

Please reflect upon the day and indicate if you engaged in any of the following mathematics-related leadership activity. Please consider the follow-up prompts.

Over the course of today, did you engage in any work related to:

1. Curating and/or (re)developing the Plain Scoile for mathematics: YES NO

a. Was this a pre-planned action? _____

b. When did it happen? _____

c. How much time did it require? _____ mins

d. Which expertise did you draw on to engage with the task? _____

e. Rate your effectiveness: _____

2. Articulating the school's agreed vision for the teaching and learning of mathematics: YES NO

a. Was this a pre-planned action? Yes

b. When did it happen? DC

c. How much time did it require? 15 mins

d. Which expertise did you draw on to engage with the task? FS, PR, OS, CK

e. Rate your effectiveness: SE

3. Coordinating ongoing School Self-Evaluation processes in numeracy: YES NO

a. Was this a pre-planned action? Yes

b. When did it happen? BC, AC, DC

c. How much time did it require? 15 mins

d. Which expertise did you draw on to engage with the task? FS, OS, PR, CK

e. Rate your effectiveness: E

4. Procuring, organising or distributing resources to teach mathematics: YES NO

a. Was this a pre-planned action? No

b. When did it happen? BC

c. How much time did it require? 5 mins

d. Which expertise did you draw on to engage with the task? CK, OS

e. Rate your effectiveness: E

Note. Abbreviations: **BC:** Before Contact/Teaching time, **DC:** During Contact/Teaching time, **AC:** After Contact/Teaching time, **FS:** Facilitation Skills, **PK:** Pedagogical Knowledge, **OS:** Organisational Skills, **CK:** Content Knowledge, **E:** Effective, and, **SE:** Somewhat Effective.

The Research Findings

The data-analysis process led to the generation of five overarching thematic findings:

Differing leaders, different activity emphases

Unsurprisingly, mathematics leaders were revealed as an industrious cohort across the twelve leadership activity domains identified within this study. Different types of leaders appeared to have more favoured aspects of their role. Principals and assistant principals tended to prioritise school development planning and numeracy-focused school self-

evaluation requirements. They also made greater efforts to promote mathematics-specific professional development in their schools. Volunteer leaders were less enamoured with such administration, and were most prolific in offering informal mentoring to colleagues and in ensuring that mathematics equipment was readily accessible to co-teachers. These insights reinforce the international literature's assertion that the nature of mathematics leadership is mainly context sensitive - local leaders attempt to respond in a manner that is simultaneously cognisant of their school's particular needs, and their professional duty to prioritise what is most important therein.

PD Please, But Not As We Know It!

There exists a palpable hunger for a previously unexperienced form of professional development for mathematics leaders. This appetite is matched by an equally strong frustration with a current professional development offering that is solely focused on enhancing pedagogical know-how. Participants expressed a need for multi-faceted upskilling which encapsulates strengthening personal mathematics competency, enhancing interpersonal skills, building data-analysis and strategic planning nous, and cultivating a broader appreciation of the STEM configuration. The desire to interact with other mathematics leaders, and to build a community in order to support and share good practice was a recurring exhortation.

Mathematics Leadership and its Skill Set – Expert or Not?

Across eight mathematics leadership skills identified in the literature, participants revealed themselves as specialised and accomplished professional leaders. Simultaneously drawing on mathematical (both pedagogical and subject-matter based), analytical, interpersonal and logistical skillsets, this multi-disciplinary demand was evident in almost all of the captured leadership acts. This does not discount the more menial, logistical aspects of mathematics leadership which were ubiquitous in all settings. Despite a humble dismissal of the suggested expert tag by all participants, it is clear that mathematics leadership requires a skillset and a personal sense of mission which goes significantly beyond the norm.

The 'Do As I Say, Not As I do' Paradox.

Occasionally, the profiled leaders were unable or unwilling to make good on their intentions to lead in specific activity domains. Conversely, duties dismissed as being of lesser value sometimes featured significantly in the logged actions of many leaders. Two domains of activity stood out in this anomalous context: the infrequent instances of meaningful monitoring of the mathematics teaching and learning standards on a whole-school level, and, the preponderance of leadership acts and cumulative time devoted to the management of mathematics teaching resources and equipment.

Leaders shunned opportunities to oversee teaching and learning effectiveness, despite consistently referencing its criticality. Understandable local factors, cultural sensitivities and logistical concerns were all cited as obstacles. Some teaching leaders lamented the lack of release time to visit the class of colleagues during the working day; another remarked upon

past experiences in her school where peer evaluation had ended unsatisfactorily for all parties; one leader cited the lack of written, explicit authority from the DES to visit the class of a peer. She was representative of a number of participants who felt that unless this leadership function was mandated by officialdom, supported by clear guidance, and, formally endorsed by the teaching unions, it remained unworkable. In a similar vein, some participants openly doubted the adequacy of their own mathematics knowledge base to pass judgement on the teaching of others.

On the other hand, despite downplaying its importance, many leaders devoted a considerable amount of their discretionary leadership time towards procuring, classifying, arranging and distributing mathematics resources and equipment. Interestingly, this kind of activity did serve a function as a gateway for volunteer or novice leaders to cut their teeth in school management. It should also be considered that in the case of more experienced leaders, their preoccupation with logistical duties can validly be rationalised by the human propensity “to gravitate towards doing what they know how to do” (Fink and Resnick, 2001 p.599), which may be further interpreted as remaining amicable and undemanding of colleagues.

Leading While Teaching – Mission Impossible?

It is undeniable that teacher leaders specifically are all the more effective because of their dual teaching and leading roles. They retain a foot in both camps and accrue added credibility with teaching colleagues for walking in their professional shoes. However, the primacy of their classroom function is most likely emasculating their leadership role. Participant after participant expressed profound frustration at the dearth of available time to lead. In parallel, their activity logs revealed snatched moments of leadership, shoehorned into a busy working day, sometimes occurring before and after contact time, and even during mandated breaks. This has inevitable consequences for the depth and quality of the hurried work they undertook. Significantly, participants who formed part of a mathematics leadership collective in their schools reported higher levels of role satisfaction and self-efficacy.

Recommendations

The study generated a set of recommendations which speak to an intended audience of mathematics leaders themselves, in-school management teams, boards of management, teacher support agencies, teacher unions and principal representative bodies, and the DES:

- Each school, irrespective of size, would hugely benefit from a formally appointed mathematics leader/leadership structure. Where relevant, this could entail a revitalization of the *Numeracy Link Teacher* role first envisaged by school self-evaluation guidance a decade ago.
- The DES should strongly consider the preparation of a mathematics-specific leadership framework to accompany its more generalised quality framework for school leadership and management.
- A broadly-based preparation and in-service support programme, devised and made mandatory for all aspiring and serving mathematics leaders, would provide unquestionable benefit to participants.

- Teacher unions, principal-representative bodies and other supporting agencies could collaborate to facilitate the creation of mathematics-specific leadership cells. In time, these localised collectives could become self-sustaining.
- Mathematics leaders can be encouraged to re-evaluate and prioritise the core aspects of their work. Within reason, leaders can be enabled to delegate the more clerical and logistical domains of activity that traditionally fall within their remit.
- Collaborative leadership structures, along the in-school management team (ISMT) model, provide a more sustainable form of mathematics coordination in schools. Schools, once adequately resourced by the DES, could explore the capacity of such structures.
- Dedicated release time must be made available to school leaders who, either individually or collectively, lead Mathematics in their school

All of these recommendations arising from the research are fundamentally contingent upon an acknowledgement of the local importance of the mathematics leadership role, and the potential it has to tangibly benefit the teaching and learning agenda at primary school level. It now falls upon all actors in this sphere to acknowledge these obvious truths. It is the writers' sincere hope that this study makes a small contribution to enhancing these painstakingly slow realisations.

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